

FAIR Data Entry Tool "Datenzee"

Project Goals and Objectives

FAIR Data Entry Tool is a complete solution for capturing bioinformatic metadata described by a given ontology. The questionnaire for collecting the data is generated based on the OWL model. Therefore, the data is collected in a machine-actionable way and available as RDF by default. The tool is also ready for submission of the data to a triple store, which further supports FAIR principles compliance, and also makes the metadata available for further processing and querying using SPARQL.

Project Benefits for ELIXIR CZ

The tool should help researchers in ELIXIR to collect their bioinformatics metadata in a machine-actionable way directly complying with FAIR principles F2, I1 and I2. The tool thus simplifies the process of making data FAIR. The researcher creates an ontological model that the tool accepts as an input. Then they can start using it for generating questionnaires and collecting the data.

Deliverables

The project has the following deliverables:

- D1: Solution, open-source code in public GitHub repository, Docker images for deployment in public Docker Hub
- D2: Guide how to install and maintain the solution
- D3: A case study in one domain showing the tool's functionality

D1: Solution, GitHub repository, Docker images

The solution functionality has been delivered as a functionality included within the Data Stewardship Wizard.

The source code is available on GitHub in the DSW repositories:

- [ds-wizard/engine-backend](#)
- [ds-wizard/engine-frontend](#)

The Docker images are available in the Docker Hub:

- [datastewardshipwizard/wizard-server](#)
- [datastewardshipwizard/wizard-client](#)

D2: Guide how to install and maintain the solution

We prepared a GitHub repository with the full deployment example, showing what Docker images need to be deployed and how they are connected to each other.

- [datenzee/datenzee-deployment-example](#)

D3: A case study in a selected domain showing the tool's functionality

We elaborated a case study in the domain of tensile testing together with the team from UPOL. They provided us with the metadata describing data generated by their testing machine (ripper) and we designed an ontology to describe those data. Additional metadata may be included (such as project information). This ontology can be imported into the DSW as a knowledge model and used for data entry. We also created an importer that can automatically transform the data from the machine output into the answers in the DSW questionnaire. The entered data can be then transformed into RDF triples describing them using the original ontology and submitted into a triple store.

The ontology and the importer are available in GitHub repositories:

- [datenzee/ripper-ontology](#)
- [datenzee/ripper-importer](#)

How to Use

Once the solution is deployed we can start using it through the DSW user interface.

The first step is to come up with an OWL file representing the ontology of the data we want to capture. Then, we can use the new feature developed within the project to import a knowledge model from an OWL file.

Import Knowledge Model

From OWL From file

Name

Organization ID

Knowledge Model ID

Version

Previous Package ID

Root Element

File

Or just drop it here

This will generate a new knowledge model that can already be used for the projects to enter the data. However, we can use the knowledge model editor in DSW to fine-tune it, add some additional questions, etc.

Ripper

 Settings

Ripper > Chapter > Test Case > Test Name

Expand all Collapse all

- Ripper
 - Chapter
 - Test Case
 - Test Name
 - Test Mode
 - Test Type
 - Title
 - Comment
 - Keyword
 - Product Name
 - Test File Name
 - Method File Name
 - Report Date
 - Test Date
 - Speed
 - Shape
 - No Of Batches
 - Qty Batch
 - Elastic
 - Yp Force
 - Max Disp Stroke
 - Max Disp Strain
 - Max Force
 - Break Force
 - Max Stress
 - Break Stress
 - Measurement

Question Delete

Type

Value

Title

Test Name

Text

Editor Preview

```
##### RDF:
- **Type:** `http://purl.org/ripper#testName`
##### Description:
Název prováděného testu
```

You can use markdown and see the result in the preview tab.

When does this question become desirable?

Never

Once the knowledge model is finalized and published, we can start using it for the project. Note that this needs to be done only once for each type of data we want to capture and then many projects can be created using the template.

So the next step is to create a new project using the knowledge model we've just created.

Create Project

[From Project Template](#) **Custom**

Name

Knowledge Model
R Ripper 1.0.0 x

Question Tags
There are no question tags for this knowledge model.

We can then start filling in the data in the questionnaire as usual in DSW.

My Project 👤 Share

[Questionnaire](#) [Metrics](#) [Preview](#) [Documents](#) [Settings](#)

[View](#) [Import answers](#) [Comments](#) [TODOs](#) [Version history](#) 🗨️

Chapters

- I. Chapter** 22
- ▶ Test Case

I. Chapter

1 Test Case + 🗨️

RDF:

- Type: <http://purl.org/ripper#TestCase>

1.a.1 Test Name + 🗨️

RDF:

- Type: <http://purl.org/ripper#testName>

Description:

Název prováděného testu

[Clear answer](#)

Answered less than a minute ago by Jan Slifka.

1.a.2 Test Mode + 🗨️

RDF:

- Type: <http://purl.org/ripper#testMode>

Description:

Režim testování

[Clear answer](#)

Answered less than a minute ago by Jan Slifka.

For our case study, we have some of the data coming out of a testing machine already, however, not in machine-actionable format. For that case, it is possible to implement an importer that can easily transform the data to the questionnaire answers. Therefore, we don't have to manually rewrite something we already have somewhere.

Importing to My Project

Cancel
Import

Import status: 18 questionnaire changes will be imported

Questionnaire Changes

Test Case

+ Added item

Test Name

✎ PLA_10_pct_X.xtas

Test Mode

✎ Single

Test Type

✎ Tensile

Title

✎ SEC/C_45_GSM_PM1

Comment

✎ Comment

Test File Name

✎ PLA_10_pct_X.xtas

Chapters

I. Chapter 31

▸ Test Case

I. Chapter

1 Test Case

RDF:

- Type: <http://purl.org/ripper#TestCase>

▼

1.a.1 Test Name

RDF:

- Type: <http://purl.org/ripper#testName>

Description:

Název prováděného testu

PLA_10_pct_X.xtas

Answered 1 minute ago by Jan Slifka.

Once we have the data collected, we might want to see how they look like as RDF triples. We've implemented a generic document template for DSW that can generate RDF from knowledge models based on the annotations there (those are automatically added when importing the OWL file. We just need to set that template as a default template on the project, so we can see the preview.

Default document template

D

Datenzee RDF Template 1.0.0

A template that generates RDF from KM based on annotations

×

Default document format

●

Turtle

Then, we can navigate to the preview and see the result.

Example Project

 Share

 Settings

```
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#Project_352cc431-e7fb-4cfe-9a0d-ce9dad550680> <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>
<http://purl.org/ripper#Project> .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#Project_352cc431-e7fb-4cfe-9a0d-ce9dad550680> <http://purl.org/ripper#licenseRef> "Apache-2.0" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#Project_352cc431-e7fb-4cfe-9a0d-ce9dad550680> <http://purl.org/ripper#hasContributor>
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#Contributor_ab70cecb-de29-47d0-bd1d-da9f4baabda2> .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#Contributor_ab70cecb-de29-47d0-bd1d-da9f4baabda2> <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>
<https://w3id.org/dcso/ns/core#Contributor> .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#Contributor_ab70cecb-de29-47d0-bd1d-da9f4baabda2> <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/name> "Albert" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#Contributor_ab70cecb-de29-47d0-bd1d-da9f4baabda2> <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/mbox> "Einstein" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#Contributor_ab70cecb-de29-47d0-bd1d-da9f4baabda2> <https://w3id.org/dcso/ns/core#hasContributorId>
"0000-0002-1825-0097" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#Contributor_ab70cecb-de29-47d0-bd1d-da9f4baabda2> <http://www.w3.org/ns/org#memberOf> "Project
Coordinator" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#Contributor_ab70cecb-de29-47d0-bd1d-da9f4baabda2> <https://w3id.org/dcso/ns/core#role> "Czech
Technical University in Prague" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#Project_352cc431-e7fb-4cfe-9a0d-ce9dad550680> <http://purl.org/ripper#hasTestCase>
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type>
<http://purl.org/ripper#TestCase> .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#testName> "PLA_10_pct_X.xtas"
.
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#testMode> "Single" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#testType> "Tensile" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#title> "SEC/C_45_GSM_PM1" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#comment> "Comment" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#testFileName>
"PLA_10_pct_X.xtas" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#methodFileName>
"3D_tisk.xmas" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#reportDate> "2022-11-03" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#testDate> "2022-11-03" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#speed> "5mm/min" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#shape> "Plate" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#noOfBatches> "1" .
<http://datenzee.ds-wizard.org#TestCase_30067296-8bc6-4e07-8da6-07923ca98426> <http://purl.org/ripper#qtyBatch> "1" .
```

Once we are satisfied with the result, we can generate an RDF document. The difference is that unlike the preview, the document is permanent and can also be submitted using the DSW submission service.

New Document

Name

Answered (current phase): 16/25

Answered: 16/25

Document Template

 Datensee RDF Template 1.0.0
A template that generates RDF from KM based on annotations

Format

 Turtle

Cancel

Create

After we have created the new document, we can see it in the list of the documents, download it and also submit it to the triple store using the submission service.

My Project

 Settings

Filter by name... Created

 Turtle · 2.06 kB · Datenzee RDF Template

- Download
- Submit
- View questionnaire
- Delete

The data in the triple store can then be used for further processing. We can also use some other features of DSW, such as project templates, to make this process easier for the people entering the data.

Conclusion

We have delivered the solution as an open source code available in GitHub repositories and built into Docker images available in public Docker Hub so everyone can use them. We created a guide on how to install and use the solution. We tested the solution in the domain of tensile testing and showed how to use it.

The solution proves its usefulness as FAIR data entry is necessary for the future of science. Based on this project, we are discussing a possible collaboration with ELIXIR-LU on further FAIR data entry tool development.